

ALIGNMENT of REFORMS in EDUCATION POLICY THROUGH NEP 2020 with special
reference to Punjab and Haryana

Pooja Pandey, Research Scholar, BHU Varanasi
Dr Shashi Srivastava, Associate Professor, BHU Varanasi

ABSTRACT:

India has designed and planned to adopt a new education strategy throughout the next decade of the twenty-first century called the Indian National Education Strategy (NEP-2020), under the direction of the current prime minister and an expert committee comprising people from a variety of backgrounds. The chapter discusses what the state of Punjab is going through due to its severe young unemployment, large budget deficit, and subpar methods for developing human resources through the current primary, secondary, and higher education systems, Punjab continues to face problems. The chapter's goal is to examine the historical backdrop and current circumstances that contributed to Punjab's economic and educational problems and to determine how improved alignment and coordination might address these issues. In the end, recommendations are given concerning how to successfully execute the NEP-2020 despite numerous limitations.

Keywords: NEP 2020, Indian Higher Education Policy, Implementation Strategies, Indian Higher Education System, Punjab

INTRODUCTION:

EVOLUTION OF THE EDUCATION POLICIES

Information dissemination and education delivery had a long and illustrious history in India. At least 15 universities or institutions of higher learning are known to have existed in ancient India, including Nalanda, and Mithila, to name a few. They crumbled and were completely destroyed under the relentless assaults of savage invaders and assailants. The "Gurukul" institution preserved the rich ethos of teachings and customs, nonetheless.

After India gained independence in 1947, a panel led by Dr. S. Radhakrishnan, the country's second president and one of the nation's greatest educators (Teacher's Day is observed on the anniversary of his birth), sought to revise the previous policies and bring them into accordance with the needs of the present and future. The Kothari Commission in 1966, the National Education Policy in 1968, and then in 1986, which was modified in 1992 (1986/92), Yashpal Committee in 1993, National Knowledge Commission in 2006, Tandon Committee in 2009, and 3rd NEP in 2019 were the major turning points in the evolution of educational reforms in India to shape the policies in correlation with the evolving challenges. This was done after an extended gap of nearly 18 years. Advancement have seen an enormous evolution over the past 50 years as a result of breakthroughs in technological and scientific knowledge. As education promotes social and economic advancement, a nation's school and college levels require a well-defined and

futuristic education strategy. The need for educational support across all levels necessitates an effective instructional system

The fourth of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which aims to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all," is the challenge that the National Educational Policy (NEP-2020) of India faces in its quest to elevate the nation as a developed one by supporting developmental imperatives. With the help of its new national education strategy in 2020, India is certain that it can meet this objective, regardless of social or economic status, at least by the year 2040. The goal of the new policy NEP-2020 is to improve the quality of education at every stage by revising and overhauling the existing educational structure, including policies, regulations, and control systems, with the vision of creating a platform to provide a quality school and higher education to every citizen of the country with Indian ethos and values to transform the nation into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society and global knowledge superpower. The new policy NEP-2020 is therefore anticipated to be a full reform with less material but more problem-solving abilities, creativity for innovation, interdisciplinary and holistic for unity and integrity. It depicts an overview of NEP-2020, identifies and analyses various challenges and concerns for more holistic and multidisciplinary education, the best learning environment and student support, changing the regulatory system of higher education, technology use and integration, and online & digital education. It also evaluates the implementation suggestions made in the policy. Intending to give everyone access to high-quality primary and secondary education as well as post-secondary education with the expectation of comprehensive and research-oriented advancement, NEP-2020 is an innovative and futuristic plan having both positive and negative features

The Vision of the National Education Policy for 2020

- A system of education that, by offering all students access to high-quality education, supports a just and thriving knowledge society.
- Instills skills, values, and dispositions that support responsible commitment to human rights, sustainable development and living, and global well-being, thus reflecting a truly global citizen.
- Develops a deep sense of respect towards fundamental rights, duties, and Constitutional values, bonding with one's country, and conscious awareness of one's role and responsibilities in a changing world.

PEDAGOGY

The members of the curriculum development team recommend the following strategies in addition to the traditional, time-tested lecture method:

1. Case-Based Learning: Case-Based Learning/Critical Learning Tool may provide students with practical experience. It improves students' ability to analyze organizational issues and

teaches them how to make important decisions. They acquire the ability to use concepts, principles, and analytical abilities to address issues in actual situations.

2. **Experiential/Live Projects/Grass Root Projects:** It is important to encourage students to engage in experiential projects, Live Projects, and/or Grass Root Projects in businesses, organizations, and factories to close the gap between theory and practice.

3. **Teamwork and Building:** Working in teams and fostering a sense of teamwork are crucial for internalizing the core curriculum. Students might acquire these abilities through inter-faculty interdisciplinary learning.

4. **Using ICT in global education:** With the aid of contemporary ICT, classroom instruction is moving more and more towards digitalization. Connecting with individuals via electronic means who are dispersed over the globe and who provide current information from their industry, their clients, and events in their immediate surroundings. This covers the usual content while also sparking new ideas.

5. **Leadership Development:** In addition to giving students a solid foundation in the practical areas of commerce and business, the Model Curriculum emphasizes helping students develop their New Age Leadership skills.

6. **Focus on Indian Business Models:** Over the past 20 years, several Indian Business areas and organizations have made notable contributions to the development of new business models by claiming a spot in the

LITERATURE REVIEW

The research demonstrates that to solve issues with quality and quantity, the state's education sector requires significantly more serious governmental attention than has previously been the case (Brar, 2016). (Gill, n.d. 2017) In comparison to government schools, the study indicated that the cost of such private school education was extremely expensive for households. With this load rising with education level, the state's public school system becomes increasingly unequal. To promote "quality education for all" to add value to the world, the paper highlights numerous significant flaws and implementation difficulties that need to be resolved (Kumar et al., 2021). (Aithal & Aithal, 2020) Discusses numerous prognostications on topics like creating top-notch colleges and universities, institutional restructuring and consolidation, more holistic and multidisciplinary education, the best learning environment and student support, changing the higher education regulatory system, technology use and integration, and online and digital education. Saroha & Anand (2020) witness significant changes in schools and improved enlightenment, and a new educational method was presented. He has indicated that more than just action plans and execution strategies will be needed to fill the gap between the vision and purpose.

As a result, the appropriate steps are taken to guarantee that implementation fulfills expectations. (Dundar & Lewis, 1998) Identifies the relationship between academic research productivity and institutional factors from National Research Council data in four different fields. (Aktar, 2021)

discusses the examination of the NEP 2020 provisions and management practice at the university level included in the current article. For the development and implementation of NEPs at the national and HEI (Higher Education) levels, recommendations are provided. Panditrao & Panditrao (2020) says there should be no single stream/discipline universities at the university/HEI level; instead, delivery methods should be interdisciplinary and comprehensive. One term, "University," must be used exclusively. (Sidhu, n.d. 2020) examine the historical background and current circumstances that contributed to Punjab's economic and educational problems, as well as how improved alignment and cooperation might address these issues. Integrating the local, state, and national economic and educational policies efforts, especially as it pursues economic diversification that might snare labor from the agricultural sector, is crucial to Punjab's growth.

DATA ANALYSIS

1. The highest gross enrollment ratio of students from first grade to eighth grade across India was in Delhi at 121.3 %, as compared to that the following graph it is evident that the GER of students from first grade to eighth grade in Punjab and Haryana is not much below though Punjab has more GER than Haryana. Punjab has the total gross enrolment ratio for male females of 109.6 whereas in Haryana it is 103.2.

Fig 1: Gross enrolment ratio of students from first grade to eighth grade across Haryana & Punjab in India in the financial year 2022, by gender
Source: Statista

- The number of undergraduate degree holders of the female is 56% as compared to that of males with only 44%, which can be concluded as more involvement of girls in completing their education and it is also a result of the free education to girls scheme run by Punjab Government

Fig 3: Number of undergraduate degree holders across Punjab in India in 2022, by gender
Source: Statista

- From the following table, it is evident that the difference between enrollment of students in elementary school and Sr. Secondary School is high which shows poor consistency of students in completing their education.

	Elementary School		Secondary School		Sr. Secondary School	
	G	B	G	B	G	B
Haryana	103.4	103.0	93.2	96.0	76.0	75.1
Punjab	109.8	109.4	95.4	94.8	83.1	81.2

Table 1: Gross Enrollment Ratio across Punjab and Haryana in 2021-2022
Source: Economic Survey 2022-2023

4. The following table shows the literacy rate of the rural and urban populations of Punjab and Haryana who are of 7 years and above of age. The literacy rate among the urban population is more than that of the rural which accounts for low motivation to study and more involvement of students in agricultural practices in rural areas.

	Rural		Urban		Rural+Urban	
	M	F	M	F	M	F
Haryana	85.8	66.4	92.5	81.2	88.0	71.3
Punjab	85.5	74.0	93.2	96.0	88.5	78.5

Table 2: Literacy rate (in percent) among persons of age 7 years and above
Source: NSS

5. The table below discusses the level of current attendance at different levels of education, it is maximum at the primary level and keeps on reducing till the higher secondary level.

Male/Female	Pre-primary	primary	middle	secondary	Higher Secondary	Diploma certificate	graduation	All
Haryana	6.4/7.8	34.4/32.2	19.0/20.1	14.7/13.3	11.1/16.1	3.3/1.9	10.9/14.2	100/100
Punjab	10.8/10.1	33.6/37.0	19.7/18.1	12.9/13.7	10.8/8.1	2.6/1.3	9.7/11.6	100/100

Table 3: Percentage distribution of students (age 3 to 35 years) by the level of current attendance rural +urban male/female
Source: NSS

6. Age-specific attendance ratio shows maximum attendance between 6-13 years of age where students are monitored by both parents and teachers extensively and minimum at 24-29 yrs of age.

Male/Female	3-5yrs	6-10yrs	11-13 yrs	14-17yrs	18-23yrs	24-29yrs	5-29yrs	3-35yrs
Haryana	44.4/49.2	98.2/98.6	95.0/94.3	82.8/85.4	34.4/27.9	2.6/3.0	56.9/51.1	47.3/41.9
Punjab	64.5/57.9	98.8/94.4	98.9/98.2	87.8/84.0	31.0/32.9	2.2/2.4	55.7/50.4	46.1/40.1

Table 4: Age-specific Attendance Ratio (ASAR) for different age groups urban + rural male/female
Source: NSS

SUGGESTION AND RECOMMENDATION

- The early childhood care and education program covers the first five years. It will be put into practice via Anganwadi. To begin with, Anganwadi should be transformed into a Kids Zone so that the kid may receive a sports education. Additionally, to ensure that education and health go hand in hand, one of the two Anganwadi employees should be replaced with an ASHA employee and a physiotherapist. According to some estimates, 85% of brain growth happens during this time. Therefore, it will be necessary to provide the youngsters at this time with competent instruction to develop a strong and capable generation in this.
- In the primary stage, students will get instruction from third to fifth grade. The age range of visitors is between 8 and 11 years old. In this class, the youngsters should have a bagless education policy so that instead of a burden on their shoulders they have a memory and learn from the stories, poems, and experiences in the classroom.
- The youngster gains environmental information throughout the secondary school period. The government provides youngsters with midday meals in addition to bicycles. In rural areas of Punjab and Haryana, many children are unable to complete their education while working in agriculture because of the economic issues; therefore many of the students discontinue their studies in the middle of their journey.
- With the proper guidance of parents and Teachers, Sexual Education should also be imparted to in the higher secondary stage.
- With 5+3+3+4 pedagogy it is better to implement 5+3+4+3 so that students can spend 4 years in the middle stage so that they get more time in the middle stage which is most crucial, and 3 years in the secondary stage.
- Instead of targeting 50% GER in higher secondary education, a GER of more than 70% should be attained.
- The Central and State Governments should similarly provide institutions special incentives to boost the Gross Enrolment Ratio.

CONCLUSION

The entire NEP program is an update for the weaknesses that have existed in the system of education for the last 35 to 36 years. The execution of the NEP and the stakeholders' acceptance of it will determine whether it is a success or a failure. It calls on us to work together to enhance the system. Although private unaided schools appear to be nearly entirely uncontrolled, they contribute significantly to the delivery of education in the state. In comparison to government schools, home spending is quite expensive, and this load rises with the degree of education. The survey further mentioned that even at the primary level, the government institutions in the state are not offering 'free' education. As a result, the current situation of high family costs for

pursuing a school education forces families to decide whether to register their children in schools or not, which as a result serves as a barrier to implementing state-wide universal education. The decision of families to enroll their boys in private schools as opposed to public schools at different levels of education and the resulting gender bias in schooling are also primarily explained by the high expense of private education.

The state's educational system has to be made more equitable, and the government must play a bigger part in ensuring that everyone has the chance to sign up for and attend school. Additionally, government schools need to be considerably improved to become the first choice for all societal sectors, rather than just being a low-cost alternative for parents.

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